

RELATIONSHIP OF DEATH ANXIETY AMONG MOTHERS WITH SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE: MEDIATIONAL ROLE OF MEANING IN LIFE AND SECURE ATTACHMENT TO GOD

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Abstract

Introduction: Death anxiety, a basic human concern, has a substantial effect on psychological health. It is a state of mind that is present from birth, endures throughout life, forms the basis of all worries and emerges when people realize they will die and that they might lose both themselves and the world. The purpose of this study was to explore the relationship between death anxiety and spiritual intelligence with the mediating role of the meaning in life and secure attachment to God among Pakistani Muslim mothers.

Method: This cross-sectional study is carried out in 2025 on 130 mothers in Punjab, Pakistan. This study uses the Attachment to God Scale, the Meaning in Life Questionnaire, the Death Anxiety of Mothers Scale, and the Spiritual Intelligence Self-Report Inventory. Analysis of the data was done using path analysis and the Pearson correlation coefficient.

Results: The findings indicated a significant *negative* relationship between death anxiety and spiritual intelligence. Furthermore, the association between spiritual intelligence and death anxiety have been mediated by the two variables of secure attachment to God and meaning in life. The importance of the study hypotheses were confirmed by the final research model's goodness-of-fit indices, which showed an excellent fit.

Conclusions: According to the findings, organizing educational programs, developing targeted psychological interventions and community-based settings for mothers may help reduce their fear of dying and improve their spiritual intelligence. Mothers' death anxiety can be lessened and their quality of life enhanced by this action.

INTRODUCTION

Life and death are often shown as two sides of the same coin, despite their close relationship. Unfortunately, many individuals view mortality as a taboo topic and may be reluctant to bring it up. For instance, people take great care to steer away

of terms like "death" and "dying" while discussing mortality. Rather, euphemisms are used to conform to social norms while communicating a more agreeable sense. Phrases like "passed away," "kicked the bucket," "went to a better place,"

"moved on," and "lay to rest" are used while discussing death. Therefore, for many people in today's culture, the idea of death or dying is disturbing and, to some degree, frightening (Corr & Nabe, 2003).

According to Lehto and Stein (2009), death has always been a major concern for people and has been seen as the inspiration for a lot of philosophical study and creative production. We all understand as individuals that our lives are finite and that we need to adapt accordingly. Patients with life-limiting illnesses, like advanced cancer or heart failure, should pay special attention to this since worsening symptoms may serve as a warning sign of impending death (Barrera & Spiegel, 2014). Existential concerns may arise in such a circumstance. The term "death anxiety" refers to the worry produced by the particular problem of death awareness (Abdel-Khalek, 2005). People worry about death because they believe it is an uncontrollable event. This anxiety is referred to as death anxiety. It is linked to the fear of death and is described as a negative and uneasy feeling that one has when contemplating death and dying (Wink & Scott, 2005).

The rich tapestry of motherhood is made up of threads of unfailing support, unconditional love, and unending sacrifice. A child's social-emotional development, cognitive progress, and general well-being are greatly impacted by their mother, who acts as their primary caretaker and emotional anchor from the very beginning (Izzati et al., 2024). Therefore, a mother's death dread frequently stems from her self-preservation as well as her altruistic worry for her children's ongoing well-being and protection (Musa, 2021).

Based on the theories of Sigmund Freud's 12 followers, Becker (1973) investigated the universality and innateness of fear of death in humans. These studies were combined to create the terror management theory (TMT), which brought these psychoanalytic theories into a more testable and falsifiable framework. People employ two different kinds of defence mechanisms to prevent themselves from thinking about dying, according to Greenberg et al. (1993). There are two types of defence: proximal and distal.

Maintaining a cultural worldview and boosting self-esteem are two forms of distal protection. Following cultural global perspectives helps people avoid the fear of dying by showing them the purpose of life. At the same time, it is thought that boosting one's self-esteem is a cognitive attempt to protect against the fear of dying by making one feel more valuable and invulnerable to their own existential threat. According to Greenberg et al. (1997), proximal protection is an attempt to repress thoughts of death and also to push such anxieties into the future.

The most important variable related to death anxiety is spiritual intelligence. Spiritual intelligence is described as the ability to use spiritual resources for problem-solving and goal-attainment, according to Zohar & Marshall's perspective, a foundational theory in the subject. According to this view, spiritual intelligence allows people to access their spiritual resources and find inner peace by emphasising qualities like profound self-awareness, existential and critical thinking, and a relationship to something greater than themselves (Zohar & Marshall, 2002). Additionally, this intelligence offers a thorough and meaningful viewpoint on life's objectives, encounters, and occurrences, resulting in a greater sense of self-awareness (Afrashteh & Rezaei, 2021).

The meaning in life is another important factor associated with death anxiety. Current psychology studies have attempted to comprehend and elucidate the idea of the meaning of life (Damásio & Koller, 2015). One of the fundamental human motivations is the meaning in life (Borawski et al., 2021). The strength and intensity of people's desire and efforts to develop or deepen their knowledge of the meaning, significance, and purpose of their existence is characterised as the search for meaning in life (Steger et al., 2008). According to Viktor Frankl's idea of logotherapy, one of the primary motivations for people is their search for meaning in life. Frankl thought that by finding purpose in life, people may continue to live and grow emotionally even under the most difficult circumstances. This perspective highlights the significance of meaning-seeking as a dynamic

and impactful activity on psychological well-being (Frankl, 1963).

Secure attachment to God is another crucial factor associated with death anxiety. Kirkpatrick (1992) used the terms "haven of safety and secure base" to define the characteristics of an attachment figure to examine and evaluate attachment to God relationship. He suggested that when people are in adverse or stressful conditions, they turn to God and God function as haven of safety for believers. Researchers started using attachment theory in the social scientific study of religion because strong links between people and God fit the requirements for attachments, just like parent-child relationships do (Rowatt and Kirkpatrick 2002).

Numerous research have looked at the overall relationship between death anxiety and other factors in recent years. Studies show a significant inverse connection between symptoms of depression and thoughts of death anxiety and spirituality (Aderyani et al., 2021). Data analysis in a study by Waheed Elzo Hairry et al. in Egypt made it abundantly evident that persons' spiritual health level and death anxiety had a significant inverse association (Elzohairy et al., 2022). A negative and significant relationship between experiences of spirituality and spiritual state and death anxiety has also been confirmed by several studies (Taghiabadi et al., 2017; Rababa et al., 2021). Furthermore, research conducted in South Korea by Jo et al., 2019 showed a strong and direct link between spiritual well-being and the meaning in life.

Studies have indicated a noteworthy inverse relationship between spiritual intelligence and fear of dying (Salmani & Zoghi, 2022). According to the results of a study by Abedi et al., there is a strong positive relationship between religious well-being and life's meaning, existential well-being and life's meaning, and spiritual well-being and life's meaning (Abedi et al., 2014).

Chang et al., 2021 explored a model that emphasized the involvement of death fear in the experience of meaning through prosocial behaviors and the search for meaning. The findings demonstrated three ways in which death anxiety influences the experienced meaning:

directly through the pursuit of meaning in the first path, through prosocial behavior in the second path, and in turn through the search for meaning and prosocial behavior in the third path, which accounted for the largest portion of the overall effect.

The goal of this study is to find out the novel outcomes and pathways for the impacts of death anxiety. The significance of death anxiety among mothers, the role of death anxiety in predicting spiritual intelligence, and the importance of secure attachment to God and the meaning in life as potential mediators in this relationship, all point to the need for this research, in accordance with theoretical perspectives and previous studies. Studies on these variables are found in other nations and on other samples. However, in Pakistan there is no enough studies on these variables. And if researches are present, these are limited especially the mediational role of secure attachment to God. Present study will offer perception in these variables and additionally open new methods for other researchers to explore the impact of these variables among mothers. Despite the fact that several studies have looked at each of these characteristics separately, none have looked directly at the connections between the current variables in combination. In light of this, the current study attempts to address the following question: How do death anxiety and spiritual intelligence relate to one another, with the role of secure attachment to God and meaning in life acting as a mediator?

Hypothesis

1. Death anxiety would be negative predictor of spiritual intelligence.
2. Death anxiety would be negative predictor of meaning in life.
3. Meaning in life would be positive predictor of spiritual intelligence.
4. Death anxiety would be negative predictor of attachment to God.
5. The relationship between death anxiety and spiritual intelligence would be mediated by secure attachment to God.

6. The relationship between death anxiety and spiritual intelligence would be mediated by meaning in life.

Method

Study design and participants

The time frame for this cross-sectional study was July 26, 2024 to August 24, 2025. The study obtained ethical approval from the University of Sargodha, Department of Psychology and Institutional Review Board. All procedures were carried out with sufficient knowledge. Every treatment was carried out in compliance with the Declaration of Helsinki, guaranteeing participant comprehension and acquiring each person's informed permission. All mothers in Punjab, Pakistan, made up the study's population. Convenient sampling technique were used for selection of participants based on inclusion criteria, which included mothers. Exclusion criteria contained unmarried women and married women without children. The data collection process involved administering a Google and hard copy of form to the mothers. Before participating, the participants were assured of the confidentiality of their responses and provided with an informed consent form. They were informed that their responses would only be used for research purposes and had the option to decline participation. Participants were requested to provide genuine and original responses. Initially, study involved 282 mothers with age varying from 19 to 65 ($M = 37.47$, $SD = 9.88$). However, our final analysis was conducted on a sample of 270 respondents, as 12 respondents were excluded because of incomplete or randomly filled responses, which ensured the integrity of our data. Respondents were also questioned regarding their age, marital status, education, residence, family system, duration of marriage, number of children and other sociodemographic variables at the start of study.

Instruments

Meaning in Life Scale (Steger & Fraizer, 2006)

Steger and Fraizer (2006) developed the Meaning in Life Scale. This Scale consists of 10 items that measures the presence of and search for meaning

in life. There were five items in the first subscale (1, 4, 5, 6, & 9) and five items in the second subscale (2, 3, 7, 8, & 10) respectively. It is 7 point Likert scale, with 1 representing absolutely untrue and 7 representing absolutely true. The coefficient alpha for this sample was .88.

Death Anxiety of Mothers Scale (Zahra & Ghayas, 2025)

Death Anxiety of Mothers Scale was developed by Zahra & Ghayas (2025). This Scale comprised of 9 items that assess the death anxiety of mothers. It has two subscales. The first subscale is children-oriented that comprised 6 items. The second subscale is self-oriented that comprised 3 items. It is five point Likert scale, with 0 indicating "never" and 4 indicating "always". The coefficient alpha of this scale is 0.87. Higher score on this scale indicates higher level of death anxiety among mothers and vice versa.

Attachment to God Scale

This scale is developed by Rowatt (2002). The participant's level of connection to God was assessed using the attachment to God Scale (Rowatt, 2002). Nine items made up the scale, which measures two aspects of attachment: anxious attachment and avoidance (versus secure) attachment. Items 2, 7, 9, 1r, 4r, and 6r (the letter "r" denotes reverse-coded items that measure secure attachment to God) are used to measure avoidance attachment, whereas items 3, 5, and 8 are used to measure anxious attachment. "Strongly disagree" is represented by a 5, and "strongly agree" by a 1. Reliability for the secure attachment to God was .88 in this sample

Spiritual Intelligence Self-Report Inventory (SISRI)

SISRI was constructed by King in 2008. There are 24 items on this inventory, and there are five possible answers ranging from 0 to 4, where 0 means the subject is not true at all and 4 means the subject is true totally. SISRI has a range of 0-96. Transcendental Awareness (TA): Items 2, 6, 10, 14, 18, 20, and 22 (ranging from 0-28); Conscious State Expansion (CSE): Items 4, 8, 12, 16, and 24 (ranging from 0-20); Critical Existential Thinking (CET): Items 1, 3, 5, 9, 13, 17, and 21

(ranging from 0-28); and Personal Meaning Production (PMP): Items 7, 11, 15, 19, and 23 (ranging from 0-20). The SISRI's coefficient alpha in this sample is .91.

Statistical Analysis

The computation of descriptive statistics, such as mean and standard deviation, was part of the data analysis process. Using SPSS v.26, Pearson correlation coefficients were used to analyse the associations between variables, and AMOS was used for path analysis and hypothesis testing. Important presumptions were confirmed prior to starting the path analysis. The skewness index was used to evaluate the dependent variables' normality; both variables' values fell between the

allowed range of -1 and +1, suggesting a normal distribution. This finding reinforces the notion of normality, even though its impact decreases with increasing sample numbers. The research met the assumption that the endogenous variables' errors were independent of one another by finding no significant correlations between them. An interval scale was used to measure each variable. Chi-square, Chi-square/df, Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis Index [TLI, also called the non-normed fit index (NNFI)], Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) and Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) were among the indices used to assess the model fit. Good model fit is indicated by values of RMSEA that are near to 0 and CFI and GFI values that are closer to 1

Results

Table 1

Coefficient Alpha, Standard Deviation, Mean, and Descriptive of Death Anxiety of Mothers Scale, Attachment to God Scale, Spiritual Intelligence Scale, Meaning in Life Scale (N = 130)

Variables	M	SD	α
DAMS	21.6615	9.46028	0.86
Children-oriented	14.7846	7.12783	0.88
Self-oriented	6.8769	4.01164	0.83
Secure Attachment	13.6846	6.92041	0.88
SISRI	56.9385	16.63878	0.91
MLS	48.6615	13.95539	0.88
PM	23.2385	6.72702	0.82
SML	13.0077	4.49029	0.71

Abbreviations: DAMS, *Death Anxiety of Mothers Scale*; MLS, *Meaning in Life Scale*; PM *Presence of Meaning*; SML, *Search for Meaning in Life*; SISRI, *Spiritual Intelligence Self Report Inventory*.

The table 1 shows mean, standard deviation, and reliability of the measures employed in this study. The alpha reliability of all coefficients were > .70.

Table 2. Pearson Correlation of DAMS with related scales (N = 130)

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. DAMS	—	0.91***	0.71***	-0.34***	-0.38***	-0.38***
2. Children-oriented	—	—	0.38***	-0.26***	-0.34***	-0.35***
3. Self-oriented	—	—	—	-0.33***	-0.30***	-0.26***

4. Secure Attachment	–	–	–	–	0.18*	-0.02
5. SIRSI	–	–	–	–	–	0.71***
6. MLS	–	–	–	–	–	–

Abbreviations: DAMS, Death Anxiety of Mothers Scale; MLS, Meaning in Life Scale; SIRSI, Spiritual Intelligence Self Report Inventory

Pearson correlation between the variables is displayed in the Table 2. Death Anxiety of Mothers, the main scale, exhibited strong positive correlations with its subscales, Children-oriented ($r=0.92$, $p<0.001$) and Self-oriented ($r=0.72$, $p<0.001$), while the two subscales themselves showed significant positive correlation ($r=0.39$, $p<0.001$). Furthermore, the main scale showed significant negative correlations with convergent variables such as Secure Attachment ($r=-0.35$,

$p<0.001$), Spiritual Intelligence ($r=-0.39$, $p<0.001$), and Meaning in Life ($r=-0.39$, $p<0.001$). Similarly, the Children-oriented subscale displayed significant negative correlations with Secure Attachment ($r=-0.28$, $p<0.001$), Spiritual Intelligence ($r=-0.35$, $p<0.001$), and Meaning in Life ($r=-0.36$, $p<0.001$). The Self-oriented subscale also showed significant negative correlations with Secure Attachment ($r=-0.34$, $p<0.001$), Spiritual Intelligence ($r=-0.31$, $p<0.001$), and Meaning in Life ($r=-0.27$, $p<0.001$).

Table 3
Path coefficients for direct and indirect effect of Death Anxiety, Search for Meaning secure attachment to God with Spiritual Intelligence

Paths	Coefficient β	P-value	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower	Upper
Death Anxiety → Secure attachment to God	-0.35	0.001	-0.51	-0.18
Death Anxiety → Meaning in life	-0.45	0.001	-0.59	-0.29
Secure attachment to God → Meaning in life	-0.17	0.017	-0.3	-0.03
Secure attachment to God → Spiritual intelligence	0.20	0.001	0.10	0.30
Meaning in Life → Spiritual intelligence	0.71	0.001	0.62	0.78
Death anxiety → Secure attachment to God → Spiritual intelligence	-0.07	0.000	-0.14	-0.02
Death anxiety → Meaning in life → Spiritual intelligence	-0.27	0.001	-0.37	-0.17

Table 3 depicted standardized and unstandardized coefficients for different direct and indirect effects computed in Amos. The direct effects of death anxiety on secure attachment to God and meaning in life are significant and negative. The direct effects of secure attachment to God on meaning in life are significant and negative. The direct effects of secure attachment to God on spiritual intelligence are significant and positive. The direct

effects of meaning in life on spiritual intelligence are significant and positive. Different variables mediated the relationships of death anxiety with other variables. The indirect effects of death anxiety through secure attachment to God on spiritual intelligence are significant and negative. In the same way, the indirect effect of death anxiety through meaning in life on spiritual intelligence is significant and positive.

Figure 1 depicts conceptual framework of the present research. Death anxiety exhibited direct negative effect on secure attachment to God and meaning in life. Secure attachment to God, in turn, demonstrated a direct negative effect on meaning in life and direct positive effect on spiritual intelligence. Meaning in life exhibited direct positive effect on spiritual intelligence.

Moreover, meaning in life significantly mediated the relationship between secure attachment to God and spiritual intelligence. Additionally, secure attachment to God significantly mediated the relationship between death anxiety and spiritual intelligence. Also, secure attachment to God significantly mediated the relationship between death anxiety and meaning in life.

Table 4. Model fit indices of model testing

Indexes	Chi-square	df	CFI	GFI	TLI	RMSEA
Model	1.12	1	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.03

df= degree of freedom; CFI= Comparative Fit Index; RMSEA= Root Mean Square Error of Approximation; GFI Goodness of Fit Index; TLI=Tucker Lewis Index Table 4 shows the findings of factor loadings and model fit indices of CFA for Death Anxiety of

Mothers Scale. The model's fit indices and parameters were estimated using the Principal Axis Factoring technique. With chi-square 1.12 (df=1), CFI=.99, GFI .99, and RMSEA =.03, the model demonstrated a strong fit to the data based

on the original criteria. Good model fit is indicated by values of RMSEA that are near to 0 and CFI and GFI values that are closer to 1. There are 9 items in the final model.

Discussion

The current study investigated a potential mediating role of secure attachment to God and the meaning in life in the relation between spiritual intelligence and death anxiety. The results showed that death anxiety is significantly predicted by all three factors: secure attachment to God, spiritual intelligence, and the pursuit of meaning. Furthermore, the association between spiritual intelligence and death anxiety is mediated by secure attachment to God and meaning in life. First hypothesis of the study is supported by the results claiming that death anxiety would be negative predictor of spiritual intelligence. According to studies, death anxiety and spiritual intelligence were found to be negatively and significantly correlated. In other words, people with higher level of death anxiety have lower level of spiritual intelligence. Research by Salmani & Zoghi, 2022 in Egypt, found a negative and significant correlation between death anxiety and spiritual experiences in an Iranians, which is consistent with the findings of this study. To explain this discovery, Terror Management Theory states that awareness of mortality results in extreme fear, which in turn creates psychological issues and a loss in adaptive psychological functioning (Solomon, 1991). As a result, these people's awareness of mortality lowers their spiritual well-being and heightens their death fear (Jo et al., 2019). When a person leads a life with a high degree of spirituality, their fear of dying is lessened and their spiritual intelligence is revealed (Levin, 2000).

The second hypothesis was supported by different researches. The studies support the notion that confronting mortality causes people to start thinking about life's purpose (Geçtan, 2005; Sigrist, 2015). This conclusion is supported by the findings of earlier research. Lyke (2013) examined fear of dying and their desire for meaning in life. He discovered that there was significant

correlation with fear of dying and search for meaning in life.

The third hypothesis, which proposed a significant and positive relationship between spiritual intelligence and the meaning in life, was likewise supported. In other words, level of spiritual intelligence rises in accordance with their quest for a meaning in life. This result is consistent with research by Abedi et al., 2016, who discovered a positive and significant correlation between spiritual health and life meaning in the population of an Iranian city, and by Jo et al., 2019, who showed a positive and significant relationship between spiritual well-being and the search for meaning among South Korean students. One way to explain these findings is to suggest that life strategies, value systems, and spiritual self-actualization are all significantly influenced by the meaning in life. According to Frankl, people actively look for meaning in life, which aids them in determining their direction and purpose amidst obstacles. By enhancing skills like self-awareness and critical thinking, this approach not only alleviates pain and existential fears but also fosters spiritual intelligence (Steger, 2008; Emmons, 2000). Furthermore, the notion of the search for meaning is strongly related to spirituality and raises the spiritual intelligence of people by enhancing their spiritual life.

This study also confirmed another hypothesis by showing a strong and positive relationship between death anxiety and secure attachment to God. People with a secure relationship with God are less likely to experience psychological disturbances, anxiety, loneliness, and depression (Baratpour & Naderi, 2023). Aghajani et al.'s 2019 study found that attachment to God significantly correlated negatively with death anxiety. According to the research done by Nasiri et al. (2019), people who have a stronger sense of secure attachment to God are more likely to have a positive outlook on death and experience mental calm.

Fourth hypothesis of the study is supported by the results claiming that the relationship between death anxiety and spiritual intelligence would be mediated by secure attachment to God. According to the prior findings, spiritual intelligence and

attachment to God are directly and favorably related. This implies that the people who have secure attachment to God are spiritually more intelligent than those who have insecure attachment to God (Bagheri et al., 2011). According to Mohammadzadeh et al., 2015, those who have lower level of death anxiety show secure attachment to God.

The explanation for the mediating role of the meaning in life is that people feel more in control of their emotional distress and turmoil when they find a purpose and meaning for their lives or improve them, which can lessen their fear of dying and help them become more spiritually intelligent (Nasab, 2022). This is because people have a diminished capacity to control some unfavourable circumstances. Additionally, facing life's obstacles and important issues promotes introspection and deeper thought, which speeds up spiritual intelligence.

Additionally, the current study's research approach is both distinct and consistent with the Chang et al., 2021 model. The present study examined the impact of death anxiety from the path of the search for meaning and secure attachment to God on spiritual intelligence, whereas Chang's model concentrated on the potentially mediating role of the search for meaning and social behaviors in the relationship between death anxiety and experienced meaning. The current model has investigated broader and more in-depth aspects of this relationship by including other factors. Both research stress that there are some connections between spirituality and death anxiety.

Limitations

1. Self-reported inventories were used to collect data for the current study's variables, which increases their social desirability and poses a serious risk to internal validity.
2. Response biasness or social desirability was not controlled in the present study. The results of the current study may have been skewed by the social desirability effect, particularly in the notion of spiritual intelligence. Respondents were more likely to report higher degree of spiritual intelligence on self-report instruments in Pakistan,

where spirituality is particularly important because there are more Muslims in the country.

3. The study may not adequately consider the influence of cultural factors on spiritual intelligence and its relationship with other variables. Cultural variations in spirituality may affect the findings and limit the generalizability across different cultures or ethnicities.
4. Since all of the study's participants were residents of Punjab, the sample of the current study is rather small. The population of one province is not always representative of Pakistan as a whole, thus conclusions from this study should not be generalized.
5. The study may not account for all possible confounding variables that could influence the relationship between religiosity and health-related quality of life.

Suggestions

1. To combat response biases or reduce social desirability and increase internal validity, more than one research design should employed.
2. The researcher gathers data from several cities or makes an effort to gather from every province in Pakistan in order to generalize the research to the entire population of Pakistan.
3. Researcher should try to remove all possible confounding by doing the advanced level of research.
4. The researchers should focus on qualitative aspects of research as well.
5. Large sample sizes should be used in future studies to maximize the external validity of the findings.
6. In order to determine the direction of causal influences, longitudinal research design should be used to evaluate the causal effects of the hypothesized predictors of life satisfaction and health-related quality of life.

Implications

The findings can be used to develop targeted psychological interventions with the purpose of reducing death anxiety in mothers. By highlighting the crucial roles of meaning in life and secure attachment to God, the study provides a clear roadmap for therapists and counselors. For

instance, therapeutic programs could focus on helping mothers find a greater sense of purpose and meaning, or strengthen their spiritual beliefs and their attachment to God, which in turn could help them cope with death-related fears. The study also has important implications for clinical practice, as it suggests that an individual's spiritual beliefs and sense of purpose should be considered as part of a holistic approach to mental health. Additionally, these insights can be utilized in educational and community-based settings to foster spiritual among mothers, ultimately promoting their psychological well-being.

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